

MetaboMiNR User Guide

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Table of Contents

Step 1: Data upload.....	2
Step 2: Global Analysis.....	4
Step 3: Metabolism Miner.....	6
Step 4: Nuclear Receptor Miner.....	8
Step 5: Individual Plotter.....	10

Step 1: Data upload

1. MetaboMiNR can intake LFQ data from a MaxQuant analyzed experiment. Within the MaxQuant output, you will find a file named “proteinGroups.txt”. The typical path for this file is ~\combined\txt\proteinGroups.txt.

MetaboMiNR Welcome Global Analysis Metabolism Miner Nuclear Receptor Miner Individual Plotter

MetaboMiNR

Welcome to MetaboMiNR

Authors: Michael F. Saikali, Carolyn L. Cummins
Affiliation: Cummins Lab, Leslie Dan Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Toronto
MetaboMiNR is a web application for the rapid analysis of MaxQuant LFQ experiments with a focus on Nuclear Receptors (NRs) and metabolism.

Getting Started

To start analysis, you will need your proteinGroups.txt file that MaxQuant generates. Start by ensuring that your sample names all start with a non numeric character or contain a character in them. (For example: 001 as a sample name will not work but MS001 or 001MS would work). Upload your data using the file uploader below. The application will read your data file and generate a template for you to indicate the sample groups (see figure below). Download the template in step 2 and input your condition for each sample and the replicate number.

Downloaded conditions file

label	condition	replicate
MS01	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS02	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS03	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS04	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS05	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS06	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS07	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS08	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS09	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS10	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS11	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS12	fill in condition	fill in replicate number

Fill in the required information offline in notepad or excel.

Upload the completed table back into MetaboMiNR

Uploaded conditions file

label	condition	replicate
MS01	Chow_Veh	1
MS02	Chow_Veh	2
MS03	Chow_LDT409	1
MS04	Chow_LDT409	2
MS05	HFD_Veh	1
MS06	HFD_Veh	2
MS07	HFD_LDT409	1
MS08	HFD_LDT409	2
MS09	HFD_Veh	3
MS10	HFD_LDT409	3
MS11	Chow_Veh	3
MS12	Chow_LDT409	3

1. Upload Data

Upload your proteinGroups.txt file.

Browse... No file selected

2. Download Template

Once your data is read, you can download this template to indicate the groupings for the samples.

Download Template

3. Upload Conditions

Upload completed condition file from step 2.

Browse... No file selected

2. To upload the file, select browse under “Upload Data” and navigate to your proteinGroups.txt file. You may rename the file if you choose, but do not edit any of the columns or column names prior to upload.

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MS04	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS05	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS06	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS07	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS08	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS09	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS10	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS11	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS12	fill in condition	fill in replicate number

Fill in the required information offline in notepad or excel.

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Uploaded conditions file

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MS03	Chow_LDT409	1
MS04	Chow_LDT409	2
MS05	HFD_Veh	1
MS06	HFD_Veh	2
MS07	HFD_LDT409	1
MS08	HFD_LDT409	2
MS09	HFD_Veh	3
MS10	HFD_LDT409	3
MS11	Chow_Veh	3
MS12	Chow_LDT409	3

1. Upload Data

Upload your proteinGroups.txt file.

Browse... proteinGroups_LDT409.jv

Upload complete

2. Download Template

Once your data is read, you can download this template to indicate the groupings for the samples.

[Download Template](#)

3. Upload Conditions

Upload completed condition file from step 2.

Browse... No file selected

- Once upload is complete, you will see a message under the uploader that displays “Upload complete”. You may then press “Download Template” which will automatically download a csv file named “ConditionTemplate.csv”. You may rename this file as you please.

	A	B	C
1	label	condition	replicate
2	MS01	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
3	MS02	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
4	MS03	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
5	MS04	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
6	MS05	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
7	MS06	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
8	MS07	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
9	MS08	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
10	MS09	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
11	MS10	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
12	MS11	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
13	MS12	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
14			

	A	B	C
1	label	condition	replicate
2	MS01	Chow_Veh	1
3	MS02	Chow_Veh	2
4	MS03	Chow_LDT409	1
5	MS04	Chow_LDT409	2
6	MS05	HFD_Veh	1
7	MS06	HFD_Veh	2
8	MS07	HFD_LDT409	1
9	MS08	HFD_LDT409	2
10	MS09	HFD_Veh	3
11	MS10	HFD_LDT409	3
12	MS11	Chow_Veh	3
13	MS12	Chow_LDT409	3
14			

- Edit the ConditionTemplate.csv template in your editor of choice, filling in each condition avoiding spaces in the condition name. Under the replicate column, indicate for each condition which sample is replicate 1, 2, 3, etc. For each condition there cannot be duplicates of the replicate number (e.g. Chow_Veh 2, and Chow_Veh 2).

MetaboMiNR | Welcome | Global Analysis | Metabolism Miner | Nuclear Receptor Miner | Individual Plotter

MetaboMiNR

Welcome to MetaboMiNR

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Getting Started

To start analysis, you will need your proteinGroups.txt file that MaxQuant generates. Start by ensuring that your sample names all start with a non numeric character or contain a character in them. (For example: 001 as a sample name will not work but MS001 or 001MS would work). Upload your data using the file uploader below. The application will read your data file and generate a template for you to indicate the sample groups (see figure below). Download the template in step 2 and input your condition for each sample and the replicate number.

Downloaded conditions file		
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MS06	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS07	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS08	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS09	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS10	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS11	fill in condition	fill in replicate number
MS12	fill in condition	fill in replicate number

Fill in the required information offline in notepad or excel.

Upload the completed table back into MetaboMiNR

Uploaded conditions file		
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MS01	Chow_Veh	1
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MS04	Chow_LDT409	2
MS05	HFD_Veh	1
MS06	HFD_Veh	2
MS07	HFD_LDT409	1
MS08	HFD_LDT409	2
MS09	HFD_Veh	3
MS10	HFD_LDT409	3
MS11	Chow_Veh	3
MS12	Chow_LDT409	3

1. Upload Data

Upload your proteinGroups.txt file.

Browse... proteinGroups_LDT409_jiv

Upload complete

2. Download Template

Once your data is read, you can download this template to indicate the groupings for the samples.

Download Template

3. Upload Conditions

Upload completed condition file from step 2.

Browse... LDT_cond.csv

Upload complete

- Upload the completed ConditionTemplate.csv file by selecting **Browse** under Upload Conditions and navigate to the completed file. Once upload is complete, you will see a progress bar that reads “Upload complete”.

Run Analysis

Run Analysis

✓

- To begin analysis, press on **Run Analysis** and wait until a green checkmark appears next to the button. Once this green checkmark appears, you may navigate to other pages.

Step 2: Global Analysis

- Using the navigation bar at the top of the page, navigate to the **Global Analysis** page.

Global Analysis

The following is a standard processing of the LFQ data for analysis. This will start with first identifying missing values and replacing them with imputed values where appropriate while discarding the proteins that do not meet our threshold. Followed by identification of differentially expressed proteins (DEPs) and principal component analysis (PCA).

Step 1: Data filtering

This will show you an overview of the # of proteins detected across the samples, and allow you to select an appropriate threshold for filtering the data.

Before Filtering

Protein identifications overlap

Number of proteins

Identified in number of samples

After Filtering

Protein identifications overlap

Number of proteins

Identified in number of samples

Select the threshold for filtering the data. For a protein to be kept it must be present in all samples in at least ONE condition (threshold=0). You can loosen the threshold to allow for a couple of missed values.

Threshold

0

- Under the data filtering section, you will find a plot showing the number of proteins identified in each sample before and after filtering for valid data. Between them is a threshold value that you can adjust. The default selection is 0 which means that for a protein to be kept in the dataset, it must be detected in ALL replicates of at least ONE condition. Increasing the threshold decreases that requirement by 1. For example, when in a 4-replicate experiment, threshold = 1 requires the protein to be detected in at least 3 out of 4 of the replicates in at least one condition.

9. The next step shows the process of imputing missing values. Missing values are usually imputed in proteomic analyses to preserve the ability to perform statistical analyses on proteins that are not present in all conditions. These values are imputed as a random value from a normal distribution taken 1.8 standard deviations below the mean of the observed values. The heatmap displays where the missing values are, allowing the user to spot a poor sample if it is consistently missing values. The histograms on the right labeled `data_rawFilter()` and `data_imputed()` show the distribution of intensities before and after imputing, respectively. You will see a new small distribution or shoulder appear on the left of the histogram representing the imputed values. The figure above to the left shows the histogram for imputing threshold of 0 compared to an imputing threshold of 2 on the right. Increasing the threshold increases the number of imputed values. ***The imputed value peak height should not exceed the real values.*** Thus, in the image above, the threshold of 2 is too high.

10. The next step includes the statistical analysis. The default cutoff for the adjusted p-value is 0.05, however you may decrease this to make the cutoff more stringent. The log₂FC cutoff is set to 0.5 by default meaning it will only highlight proteins that were greater than 0.5 or less than -0.5.

Valid contrasts are: 'Chow_LDT409_vs_HFD_LDT409', 'Chow_LDT409_vs_HFD_Veh', 'Chow_Veh_vs_Chow_LDT409', 'Chow_Veh_vs_HFD_LDT409', 'Chow_Veh_vs_HFD_Veh', 'HFD_Veh_vs_HFD_LDT409'

11. You may change the conditions plotted by selecting a different condition using the radio buttons. While the application does every possible comparison, it only does it once (e.g. it will do Chow_Veh vs Chow_LDT409 but not Chow_LDT409 vs Chow_Veh). If you have a selected an invalid comparison, reverse the selection or check the list of valid contrasts that appear with the error message.

12. The default setting for the PCA plot is to generate it using only the top 500 most variable proteins. You may use the slider bar or the text input to increase this to a maximum of the number of proteins detected in your samples allowing you to produce a PCA plot of the entire dataset.

13. The next step produces a k-means clustered heatmap. The default selection for the number of clusters is 6, but you may use the slider to adjust the number of clusters and the heatmap will adjust in real time. Additionally, you may adjust the color scaling by increasing or decreasing the maximum z-score value which sets the limits for the legend.

Step 3: Metabolism Miner

14. Navigate to the Metabolism Miner tool using the navigation bar.

The image shows the main interface of the Metabolism Miner tool. The navigation bar is the same as in the previous image. The main content area has a white background with the MetaboMiNR logo and the title 'Metabolism Miner'. Below the title is a paragraph of text explaining the tool's function. A red box highlights a dialog box with the question 'Do you need to convert the gene names to mouse?' and two radio button options: 'Convert to mouse' (selected) and 'Keep as human'. Below this is a form to 'Enter the ReactomeID' with the value 'R-HSA-191273' entered. There is also a 'Show' dropdown set to '10' and a search input field. A table lists pathways and their Reactome IDs. To the right, there is a 'Reorder the groups' section with buttons for different experimental conditions. Further right, there is a 'Select the number of clusters' dropdown set to '1'. Below that, there is a section titled 'Extracted matching genes from Reactome' with a list of gene names and a heatmap visualization showing gene expression levels across different conditions.

Do you need to convert the gene names to mouse?

Convert to mouse

Keep as human

Enter the ReactomeID

R-HSA-191273

Show 10 entries

Search:

Pathway	ReactomeID
1 Cholesterol biosynthesis	R-HSA-191273
2 Regulation of cholesterol biosynthesis by SREBP (SREBF)	R-HSA-1655829
3 Synthesis of Ketone Bodies	R-HSA-77111
4 Utilization of Ketone Bodies	R-HSA-77108
5 Glycogen synthesis	R-HSA-3322077

Reorder the groups

Chow_Veh_1

Chow_Veh_2

Chow_LDT409_1

Chow_LDT409_2

HFD_Veh_1

HFD_Veh_2

HFD_LDT409_1

HFD_LDT409_2

HFD_Veh_3

HFD_LDT409_3

Chow_Veh_3

Chow_LDT409_3

Select the number of clusters

1

Extracted matching genes from Reactome

Below is the list of genes that were part of this Reactome term. The matching proteins that were detected in the dataset are plotted in the heatmap.

Pmk Ebp Cyp51 Dhcr7 Dhcr24 Fdft1 Fdps Hmgcr Hmgcs1 Idl1 Lbr Plpp6 Lss Mvd Mvk Nsdhl Hsd17b7 Msmo1 Sc5d Arv1 Sqle Sreb1 Sreb2 Tm7sf2 Ggpps1

The heatmap shows gene expression levels across different experimental conditions. The y-axis lists genes, and the x-axis lists conditions: Chow_Veh_1, Chow_Veh_2, Chow_LDT409_1, Chow_LDT409_2, HFD_Veh_1, HFD_Veh_2, HFD_LDT409_1, HFD_LDT409_2, HFD_Veh_3, HFD_LDT409_3, Chow_Veh_3, and Chow_LDT409_3. The color scale ranges from -2 (blue) to 2 (red).

15. The Metabolism Miner pulls genes from Reactome which are stored as human gene names. The default setting in MetaboMiNR is to convert these gene names to their mouse orthologues. If you are dealing with a human sample, change this to “Keep as human”.

MetaboMiNR Welcome Global Analysis Metabolism Miner Nuclear Receptor Miner Individual Plotter

MetaboMiNR

Metabolism Miner

The metabolism miner allows you to extract gene sets from your data to visualize what happens to a particular pathway of interest. You may select a reactome pathway from the preselected list or provide your own reactomeID, and the application will fetch the genes found in that pathway, and pull them out of your dataset ("caution:" while the reactome list may be extensive, the output will be composed only of proteins actually detected in your sample. For example if geneXYZ is in reactomePathwayXYZ but it was not detected in your dataset, it will not appear in the output). You may re-arrange the columns of your data to group them accordingly. You can also increase the number of identified clusters. The result can be immediately visualized in the cuts made to the heatmap. You can download the results as a table of the extracted genes and their LFQ intensities along with what cluster they belong to.

Caution while selecting your own reactomeID. Reactome IDs sometimes contain a decimal value at the end, this must be removed.

Do you need to convert the gene names to mouse?
 Convert to mouse
 Keep as human

Enter the ReactomeID

Show entries

Search:

Pathway	ReactomeID
1 Cholesterol biosynthesis	R-HSA-191273
2 Regulation of cholesterol biosynthesis by SREBP (SREBF)	R-HSA-1655829
3 Synthesis of Ketone Bodies	R-HSA-77111
4 Utilization of Ketone Bodies	R-HSA-77108
5 Glycogen synthesis	R-HSA-3322077

Reorder the groups

- Chow_Veh_1
- Chow_Veh_2
- Chow_LDT409_1
- Chow_LDT409_2
- HFD_Veh_1
- HFD_Veh_2
- HFD_LDT409_1
- HFD_LDT409_2
- HFD_Veh_3
- HFD_LDT409_3
- Chow_Veh_3
- Chow_LDT409_3

Select the number of clusters

Extracted matching genes from Reactome

Below is the list of genes that were part of this Reactome term. The matching proteins that were detected in the dataset are plotted in the heatmap.

Pmk Ebp Cyp51 Dhcr7 Dhcr24 Fdft1 Fdps Hmgcr Hmgcs1 ldl1 Lbr Plpp6 Lss Mvd Mvk Nsdh1 Hsd17b7 Msmo1 Sc5d Arv1 Sqle Sreb1 Sreb2 Tm7sf2 Ggps1

16. To select a pathway, you can choose from the preselected pathways or enter your own ReactomeID in the textbox. Some ReactomeIDs will have a decimal and numbers at the end, remove these prior to inputting the ReactomeID into the textbox.

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Metabolism Miner

The metabolism miner allows you to extract gene sets from your data to visualize what happens to a particular pathway of interest. You may select a reactome pathway from the preselected list or provide your own reactomeID, and the application will fetch the genes found in that pathway, and pull them out of your dataset ("caution:" while the reactome list may be extensive, the output will be composed only of proteins actually detected in your sample. For example if geneXYZ is in reactomePathwayXYZ but it was not detected in your dataset, it will not appear in the output). You may re-arrange the columns of your data to group them accordingly. You can also increase the number of identified clusters. The result can be immediately visualized in the cuts made to the heatmap. You can download the results as a table of the extracted genes and their LFQ intensities along with what cluster they belong to.

Caution while selecting your own reactomeID. Reactome IDs sometimes contain a decimal value at the end, this must be removed.

Do you need to convert the gene names to mouse?
 Convert to mouse
 Keep as human

Enter the ReactomeID

Show entries

Search:

Pathway	ReactomeID
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3 Synthesis of Ketone Bodies	R-HSA-77111
4 Utilization of Ketone Bodies	R-HSA-77108
5 Glycogen synthesis	R-HSA-3322077

Reorder the groups

- Chow_Veh_1
- Chow_Veh_2
- Chow_LDT409_1
- Chow_LDT409_2
- HFD_Veh_1
- HFD_Veh_2
- HFD_LDT409_1
- HFD_LDT409_2
- HFD_Veh_3
- HFD_LDT409_3
- Chow_Veh_3
- Chow_LDT409_3

Select the number of clusters

Extracted matching genes from Reactome

Below is the list of genes that were part of this Reactome term. The matching proteins that were detected in the dataset are plotted in the heatmap.

Pmk Ebp Cyp51 Dhcr7 Dhcr24 Fdft1 Fdps Hmgcr Hmgcs1 ldl1 Lbr Plpp6 Lss Mvd Mvk Nsdh1 Hsd17b7 Msmo1 Sc5d Arv1 Sqle Sreb1 Sreb2 Tm7sf2 Ggps1

17. To re-arrange the heatmap, simply drag and drop the sample name tiles into the desired order and the heatmap will re-arrange.

The screenshot shows a web interface with a 'Download Results' button in the top left corner, highlighted with a red box. Below the button is a table with 10 columns and 14 rows of data. The columns are labeled: Cluster, Chow_Veh_1, Chow_Veh_2, Chow_Veh_3, Chow_LDT409_1, Chow_LDT409_2, Chow_LDT409_3, HFD_Veh_1, HFD_Veh_2, and H. The rows list various sample names and their corresponding values for each column. At the bottom of the table, it says 'Showing 1 to 10 of 14 entries' and has navigation buttons for 'Previous', '1', '2', and 'Next'.

	Cluster	Chow_Veh_1	Chow_Veh_2	Chow_Veh_3	Chow_LDT409_1	Chow_LDT409_2	Chow_LDT409_3	HFD_Veh_1	HFD_Veh_2	H
Lbr	1	2216200	1796900	2278000	3798600	1549127	2147700	3458400	2296800	
Ebp	1	15585000	18293000	6494100	22087000	15502000	15317000	8552700	11781000	
Tm7sf2	1	11883000	11763000	10554000	8939400	11201000	14777000	1301329	4707700	
Fdps	1	256480000	196970000	275770000	225720000	292280000	303250000	25422000	20024000	
Mvk	1	13552000	8146300	8665200	8129400	9843700	10318000	1301329	1226478	
Dhcr7	1	15314000	11821000	8141000	14949000	12785000	10313000	2897200	2853200	
Nsdhl	1	61771000	43985000	59044000	86296000	63528000	79192000	1301329	5147600	
Idi1	1	68499000	66318000	68941000	119630000	81952000	100780000	1301329	1226478	
Lss	1	12068000	9759800	11450000	22611000	15816000	19097000	1301329	1226478	
Dhcr24	1	4035700	5781000	7532500	7505900	5787500	8525100	1301329	4201800	

18. At the bottom of the page you will find a table with a download button that allows you to download the extracted data for downstream analysis.

Step 4: Nuclear Receptor Miner

19. Navigate to the Nuclear Receptor Miner page.

MetaboMiNR Welcome Global Analysis Metabolism Miner Nuclear Receptor Miner Individual Plotter

MetaboMiNR

Nuclear Receptor Miner

The nuclear receptor (NR) miner uses the consensomes generated by the signalling pathways project (SPP) to generate a list of likely target genes for specific NRs. You can select the consensome you are interested in, and if those proteins are in your dataset, they will be presented to you as part of a heatmap. The heatmap can be cut into clusters and exported for further analysis.

Percentile Cut-off
95

Show 10 entries

Search:

PathwayID	Description
11	GR Consensome (Transcriptomic)
12	MR Consensome (Transcriptomic)
13	p300/CBP Consensome (Cistromic)
14	PPAR Consensome (Transcriptomic)
15	PR Consensome (Transcriptomic)
16	RAR Consensome (Transcriptomic)

Reorder the groups

- Chow_Veh_1
- Chow_Veh_2
- Chow_Veh_3
- Chow_LDT409_1
- Chow_LDT409_2
- Chow_LDT409_3
- HFD_Veh_1
- HFD_Veh_2
- HFD_Veh_3
- HFD_LDT409_1
- HFD_LDT409_2
- HFD_LDT409_3

Download Full Results Download Results

Select the number of clusters
1

20. Similar to the Metabolism Miner page, you may select a pathway to extract and a heatmap will be produced. The order of the columns can be adjusted by dragging the sample name tiles around. The default percentile cutoff is 95th meaning only the 95th percentile and above is taken as a target gene in that consensome. You can make this more stringent by increasing the value.

MetaboMINR Welcome Global Analysis Metabolism Miner Nuclear Receptor Miner Individual Plotter

MetaboMiNR

Nuclear Receptor Miner

The nuclear receptor (NR) miner uses the consensomes generated by the signalling pathways project (SPP) to generate a list of likely target genes for specific NRs. You can select the consensome you are interested in, and if those proteins are in your dataset, they will be presented to you as part of a heatmap. The heatmap can be cut into clusters and exported for further analysis.

Percentile Cut-off:

Show entries

Search:

PathwayID	Description
11	GR Consensome (Transcriptomic)
12	MR Consensome (Transcriptomic)
13	p300/CBP Consensome (Cistromic)
14	PPAR Consensome (Transcriptomic)
15	PR Consensome (Transcriptomic)
16	RAR Consensome (Transcriptomic)

Reorder the groups

- Chow_Veh_1
- Chow_Veh_2
- Chow_Veh_3
- Chow_LDT409_1
- Chow_LDT409_2
- Chow_LDT409_3
- HFD_Veh_1
- HFD_Veh_2
- HFD_Veh_3
- HFD_LDT409_1
- HFD_LDT409_2
- HFD_LDT409_3

[Download Full Results](#) [Download Results](#)

21. By selecting Download Results, you will download a table of the data shown in the heatmap. By selecting Download Full Results, you will download a table containing the entire dataset, with the adjusted p-values for each comparison, and appended to it will be a table of the consensome results. See the figure below.

LFQ Intensities		Adjusted p-values		Consensome Percentile	
Protein ID	Intensity	Adjusted p-value	Consensome Percentile	Protein ID	Intensity
...

22. Offline, you can use this table to filter for only significantly altered proteins and plot their consensome results.

Step 5: Individual Plotter

23. Navigate to the final tab, the Individual Plotter.

24. Use the search bar to locate a gene. The table will automatically update as you narrow the search. To plot the gene, select the row and it will be highlighted in blue and automatically plotted. The p-values cannot be plotted directly on the figure but can be found in the table where you selected the gene.

25. To adjust the color of the plot you can select the group you want to edit and use the color picker to change the color and opacity.

Search for a protein of interest

Use this tool to search individual genes from your dataset and visualize them as a bar plot. The processed dataset may possess interpretation of an individual gene. You may use the search tool to find a gene of interest, select the row to visualize it. The

26. Finally, to adjust the order of the bars, drag the grey tiles around into the order that you would like them to appear.